

**Approach to synthesis and improving the solubility of a bronchodilator drug (Theophylline)
by its salts and cocrystals.**

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Theophylline is considered as one of the most important pharmacologic compounds. For a long period of times, synthetic drugs of theophylline have been used in the treatment of more severe diseases resulting from disorder in the physiological functions of pulmonary system, such as asthma and COPD. The cocrystal formation of theophylline with dicarboxylic acids such as oxalic acid, glutaric acid, maleic acid and dipicolinic acid, pyrazole dicarboxylic acid have been the leading task of the researcher. Also, the application of crystal engineering expands its cocrystal field to multi-drug resistance, enhancing drug action thereby reducing the side effects of the drugs. The crystal structure of THC monohydrate was an earlier reported one and compared with the parent (TH). The crystal and molecular structures of new Theophyllinium Nitrate (TN), and Theophyllinium Chloride (THC) salts were analyzed by single crystal X-ray diffraction method. Also a new Theophylline pyrogallol (TP) and a redetermination work of Theophylline resorcinol (TR) were studied by single crystal X-ray diffraction. The aim of present investigation is to synthesis and increase the solubility of the drug thereby improving the biological and chemical entity.

The solubility test has been carried out for both the salts and cocrystals to enhance the drug solubility and the therapeutic effectiveness of the drug. Also, the compounds were examined for its antibacterial activity and found to exhibit notable activity in TN against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Hence the new compound TN is a good candidate for the antimicrobial agent apart from its inherent Bronchodilator drug property.